

SOLAR POWER PLANTS SOLUTION TO ELECTRICITY PROBLEMS.

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Abstract. *Rational use of solar energy, availability of alternative energy sources.*

Key words: *Alternative energy sources; Solar collectors; Flat solar collectors; Vacuum solar collectors; Concentrated solar collectors; Absorber; Biconvex lens.*

СОЛНЕЧНЫЕ ЭЛЕКТРОСТАНЦИИ РЕШАЮТ ПРОБЛЕМЫ С ЭЛЕКТРИЧЕСТВОМ.

Аннотация. *Рациональное использование солнечной энергии, доступность альтернативных источников энергии.*

Ключевые слова: *Альтернативные источники энергии; Солнечные коллекторы; Плоские солнечные коллекторы; Вакуумные солнечные коллекторы; Концентрированные солнечные коллекторы; Поглотитель; Двояковыпуклая линза.*

At the beginning of the 21st century, problems related to the depletion of traditional energy sources and the deterioration of the earth's ecological condition began to appear in front of humanity. These problems have become extremely urgent and cause global concerns in the world community.

It is known that currently, energy is produced all over the world using mineral sources: oil, natural gas, coal, and nuclear fuel. At the same time, it is no secret that the demand for energy cannot be met only through the use of fossil sources, and that reserves of traditional sources of energy are gradually running out. Most experts believe that due to the global increase in energy demand, the supply of conventional sources will be exhausted by the middle of this century.

The opening of new mines as a result of technical development can only slightly delay the process of depletion of resources. It is clear that even if traditional energy reserves are not completely exhausted, due to the sharp increase in demand for them, a significant increase in prices will be observed.

The most attractive and promising among renewable energy sources is photovoltaics, that is, the direct conversion of solar energy into electricity. The sun can meet the growing energy demands of humans for many centuries, and this is now well known to the world community.

The amount of solar energy reaching the earth in an hour is more than the amount of energy consumed by mankind in a year, for this reason and in addition, the limited natural energy reserves and environmental problems increase the need to use solar energy.

Solar energy is the only source of energy that is technically convenient and does not pollute the environment. In the last decade, the use of solar energy has been increasing all over the world. Data from 2021 show that almost 5% of the world's electricity will be provided by photovoltaic solar plants. At first glance, it seems like a very small amount, but this share is growing very quickly. Decades ago, this indicator was only 1 percent, and it was mostly accounted for by developed countries. Currently, not only developed countries, but also developing countries are paying great attention to the use of solar energy.

According to the report prepared by the World Bank for 2020, in order to not only fully meet its demand for electricity, but also to produce more of it using solar power plants, almost all

countries of the world have geographical conditions and weather conditions. there is enough air and sunlight.

If we look at the history, in 1954 a unique invention was brought to life by the laboratories of Bell Telephone Company in New York. It had the ability to convert solar energy directly into electricity. It soon became economically viable not only for spaceflight, but also for everyday life purposes.

The energy crisis of the 1970s revived interest in solar power for businesses and homes. The UNESCO conference held in Paris in July 1973 was held under the motto "The Sun at the Service of Man" and gave clear information about the state of solar energy in the world. Until 1973, solar energy was only a research object for scientists, now it has become a new industry, but at that time, solar cells were not mass-produced due to the high cost of this technology. The cost of solar energy has fallen dramatically, in particular by more than 59 percent in the last ten years, opening up a wide path for businesses, organizations, and private homes to use solar energy.

Today, the People's Republic of China is leading the world in the use of solar energy. According to statistics in 2021, Australia is the world leader in the share of solar energy in the total electricity generation with 15.5 percent.

In our country, attention has been paid to the energy sector as a strategic direction, and new energy capacities have been built in recent years. Nevertheless, the increase of the population and the increase of industrial enterprises lead to an increase in the demand for electricity from year to year. It is estimated that the demand for electricity in our country will increase from the current 74 billion kWh to 110 billion kWh by 2030. Naturally, in such a situation, the use of renewable energy sources plays an important role in solving the problems.

Due to this, the use of solar energy is becoming one of the urgent issues in our country, and important practical work is being done in this regard. For example, the "Tutli" photoelectric power plant, fully developed by the French company Total Eren, is one of the large solar power plants built in Uzbekistan in 2022. Its power is 131 mW. It produces 270,000 kWh of electricity per year and supplies 140,000 households with electricity.

The construction of many such solar power plants will lead to the qualitative improvement of Uzbek solar energy to a new level. If large organizations and enterprises switch to mass use of renewable energy sources, reserves of natural resources will be preserved and the amount of damage to nature will be significantly reduced. At the same time, the use of photoelectric plants that directly convert sunlight into electricity, which is one of the sources of renewable energy, contributes greatly to the development of the economy without harming the environment.

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